

2-((2-(Pyridine-2-yl)hydrazono)methyl)phenol as sensing material for fabrication of Lu³⁺-PVC membrane ion selective electrode

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Abstract : Here a Lu³⁺-selective polymeric membrane sensor based on 2-((2-(pyridine-2-yl)hydrazono)methyl)phenol (PHMP) is described. At a pH range of 2.5–8.7, this sensor exhibits a Nernstian slope of 19.7±0.5 mV per decade in a linear range from 1.0 × 10⁻⁷ to 1.0 × 10⁻² M, with a detection limit of 7.6 × 10⁻⁸ M. The response time of the electrodes is less than 10 s, depending on the concentration of lutetium(III) ions. The sensor revealed very good selectivity for Lu^{III} in the presence of common alkaline, alkaline earth, transition, heavy metals and specially lanthanide ions. The optimum responses were found with membrane composition of 30% PVC, 66% benzyl acetate (BA) as solvent mediator, 2% PHMP and 2% sodium tetraphenyl borate (NaTPB). In order to investigate the sensors analytical applicability, the electrode were applied to the determination of fluoride ions in mouth wash preparations and also, as an indicator electrode, in potentiometric titration of lutetium(III) ions.

Keywords : Ion-selective electrode, potentiometry, sensor, PVC membrane.

Introduction

Due to widespread industrial use of lutetium, its selective determination is of vital importance. Lutetium, as an important member of the rare-earth family, is used in the production of catalysts used in oil and gas technologies and glass polish^{1,2}. Mass spectrometry (MS), inductively couple plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), inductively couple plasma atomic emission spectrometry (ICP-AES) are the available methods for the low-level monitoring of thulium ions in solutions. Isotope dilution mass spectrometry, neutron activation analysis, X-ray fluorescence spectrometry, etc., are also used in some laboratories. These methods are either time consuming, involving multiple sample manipulations, or too expensive for most analytical laboratories. Potentiometric sensors have shown to be very effective tools for analysis of a wide variety of cations, anions and molecules. They are very simple, inexpensive, and capable of producing reliable responses in a wide concentration range. Hence, the development of new ion-selective electrodes for lutetium and other lanthanide ions is a challenging task^{3–10}. There have been some reports on lutetium sensors based on

different ionophores^{11,12}. We have recently reported a number of sensors for ions of the lanthanide group elements^{13–20}. In this research, we wish to introduce a highly selective and sensitive Lu³⁺ ion selective membrane electrode with the incorporation of 2-((2-(pyridine-2-yl)hydrazono)methyl)phenol (Fig. 1) in a PVC-based membrane sensor.

Fig. 1. The PHMP structure.

Experimental

Reagents :

Reagent grade dibutyl phthalate (DBP), acetophenone (AP), nitrobenzene (NB), benzyl acetate (BA), sodium tetraphenyl borate (NaTPB), tetrahydrofuran (THF) and high relative molecular weight PVC of the highest purity available were procured from Merck and Aldrich, and used without any further treatments. Chloride and nitrate salts of the cations used (from Merck and Aldrich) were

all of the highest purity available and used without any further purification except for vacuum drying over P_2O_5 . Doubly distilled de-ionized water was used throughout the experiment.

Electrode preparation :

Membrane solutions were prepared by thoroughly dissolving 2 mg of ionophore PHMP, 30 mg of powdered PVC, 66 mg of plasticizer BA and 2 mg of additive NaTPB in 3 mL of THF. The resulting clear mixture was evaporated slowly until an oily concentrated mixture was obtained. A Pyrex tube (5 mm o.d.) was dipped into the mixture for 10 s so that a nontransparent membrane of about 0.3 mm thickness was formed²¹⁻²⁵. The tube was then pulled out from the mixture and kept at room temperature for 12 h. The tube was then filled with an internal solution of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $Lu(NO_3)_3$. The electrode was finally conditioned for 24 h by soaking in a $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ lutetium nitrate solution. A silver/silver chloride electrode was used as an internal reference electrode.

Synthesis of PHMP :

The salicylaldehyde (1 mmol, 0.12 g) was solved in hot ethanol, after that the 2-hydrazinylpyridine and catalytic amount of acetic acid were added to the solution. The mixture of reaction was refluxed for hour. Then the solid product was crystallized in solution of acetone and ethanol (1 : 1).

Emf measurements :

All emf measurements were carried out with the following assembly :

Ag-AgCl | $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ $LuCl_3$ | PVC membrane : test solution | Hg-Hg₂Cl₂, KCl (satd).

The potential measurements were made using a Corning ion analyser 250 pH/mV meter. The measurements were performed at room temperature (25.0 °C) and the activities of the species were calculated according to the Debye-Huckel procedure²⁶.

Results and discussion

The use of carriers containing nitrogen and oxygen atoms, in ISEs, is hence expected to increase their selectivity towards lanthanide ions, over those of alkali, alkaline earth, and several other metal ions, due to the great affinities of these ions towards soft coordination centers

like nitrogen.

In the preliminary experiments, PHMP was used as a neutral carrier to prepare PVC-based membrane electrodes for a number of lanthanide and some common metal ions. Among different metal ions tested, Lu^{III} with the most sensitive response seems to be suitably determined with the PVC-based membrane based on PHMP. This is most probably due to the proper size of Lu^{III} ion to the semi cavity of flexible PHMP, the selective behavior of the ionophore against lutetium ion in comparison to other metal ions, and the rapid exchange kinetics of the resulting PHMP- Lu^{III} complex.

Effect of the membrane composition :

The dependence of the sensitivity and selectivity obtained for a given ionophore is known to be significantly related to the membrane composition and the nature of the solvent mediator and additives used²⁷⁻³³. The influences of the membrane composition, the nature and amount of plasticizer, and the amount of NaTPB as lipophilic additives on the potential response of the proposed Lu^{III} sensor were therefore investigated, and the results are given in Table 1. As can be seen from Table 1, the increasing level of PHMP up to 2% resulted in large slope of the membrane (numbers 4-6), that displays larger slopes. Table 1 shows that, among the four solvent mediators (AP, NB, DBP, and BA) used, BA with lower polarity than other plasticizers gives better sensitivity. This is due to the low polarity of BA, which cannot be able to extract the trivalent ions (especially lanthanide ions). In this case the extraction of lanthanide ions will be affected only by the ionophore.

It is well established that the addition of lipophilic anions to cation-selective membrane electrodes not only diminishes the ohmic resistance and enhances the response behavior and selectivity, but also in cases where the extraction capability is poor, increases the sensitivity of the membrane electrodes³⁴⁻³⁸. The data given in Table 1 revealed that, in the absence of a proper additive, the sensitivity of the Lu^{III} membrane sensor based on PHMP is two-third of the Nernstian slope (no. 7 with a slope of 13.2 ± 0.4 mV per decade). However, the presence of 2% NaTPB as a suitable lipophilic additive will improve the sensitivity of the Lu^{III} membrane sensor considerably (no. 4 with a slope of 19.7 ± 0.5 mV per decade).

Table 1. Optimization of the membrane ingredients

Sensor No.	Composition of the membrane (wt, %)				Slope (mV/decade)	Dynamic linear range (M)
	PVC	Plasticizer	PHMP	NaTPB		
1	30	NB, 66	2	2	17.5 ± 0.6	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
2	30	AP, 66	2	2	15.4 ± 0.5	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-2}
3	30	DBP, 66	2	2	16.1 ± 0.4	1.0×10^{-5} – 1.0×10^{-2}
4	30	BA, 66	2	2	19.7 ± 0.5	1.0×10^{-7} – 1.0×10^{-2}
5	30	BA, 67	1	2	17.8 ± 0.3	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
6	30	BA, 65	3	2	19.2 ± 0.6	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
7	30	BA, 68	2	0	13.2 ± 0.4	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}
8	30	BA, 67	2	1	16.9 ± 0.3	1.0×10^{-6} – 5.0×10^{-2}
9	30	BA, 65	2	3	19.1 ± 0.5	1.0×10^{-6} – 5.0×10^{-2}

Calibration curve :

The emf response of the polymeric membrane electrode (Fig. 2) indicates its Nernstian behavior over a wide

remains constant in the pH range of 2.5–8.7. At higher pH values, the potential decreases. This is due to the formation of some hydroxyl complexes of Lu^{III} ions. At

Fig. 2. Calibration curve of lutetium electrode based on PHMP.

concentration range (1.0×10^{-7} – 1.0×10^{-2} M). The slope of the resulting calibration graph is 19.7 ± 0.5 mV per decade and detection limit defined as the concentration of lutetium obtained when the linear regions of the calibration graph are extrapolated to the baseline potential, is 7.6×10^{-8} M.

Effect of pH :

The pH dependence of the potential response of the sensor was studied in the pH range of 2.0–11.0 in the 1.0×10^{-3} M solution (the pH was adjusted using concentrated NaOH and HNO_3) and the results are shown in Fig. 3. As it is seen, the potential response of the sensor

Fig. 3. pH effect of the test solution (1.0×10^{-3} M of Lu^{3+}) on the potential response of the Lu^{3+} ion-selective electrode.

lower pH values, potential increases due to the membrane responses to hydronium ions and Lu^{III} ions.

Dynamic response time :

Dynamic response time is one of the most important factors for an ion-selective electrode. In this study, the practical response time was recorded by changing the Lu³⁺ concentration in solution, over a concentration range from 1.0×10^{-7} to 1.0×10^{-2} M and the results are shown in Fig. 4. As it is obvious, in the whole concentra-

the selectivity coefficients were in the range 5.4×10^{-3} to 4.3×10^{-4} . The obtained selectivity coefficients for mono- and di-valent cations (Na⁺, Ca²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Zn²⁺) were smaller than 3.3×10^{-3} , and thus did not affect the response of the proposed Lu³⁺ membrane electrode. It is most likely that the relatively good selectivity of the membrane electrode for Lu³⁺ ions arose from the stronger tendency of the carrier molecule for complexing with Lu³⁺ compared to other cations. The

Fig. 4. Dynamic response time of the lutetium electrode for step changes in the Lu³⁺ concentration : (A) 1.0×10^{-7} M, (B) 1.0×10^{-6} M, (C) 1.0×10^{-5} M, (D) 1.0×10^{-4} M, (E) 1.0×10^{-3} M, (F) 1.0×10^{-2} M.

tion range, the Lu³⁺ sensor reached its equilibrium response in a very short time (<10 s). This is probably due to the very fast exchange kinetics of complexation-decomplexation of Lu³⁺ with PHMP on the test solution-membrane interface.

Potentiometric selectivity :

The influence of interfering ions on the response behavior of ion-selective membrane electrodes is usually described in terms of selectivity coefficients. The potentiometric selectivity coefficients of the Lu^{III} sensor were evaluated by the matched potential method (MPM)³⁹⁻⁴⁵. The matched potential method selectivity coefficient, K^{MPM} , is then given by the resulting primary ion to interfering ion activity (concentration) ratio, $K^{MPM} = a_A/a_B$, where a_A is the initial primary ion (A) activity and a_B the activity of interfering ion (B).

The resulting selectivity coefficient values are given in Table 3. The data revealed that in the case of trivalent cations (Nd, Pr, Er, Dy, Eu, Yb, Sm, Cr and Fe ions),

Table 2. Selectivity coefficients, linearity range, detection limit and response time of the developed Lu³⁺ electrode

	This work
	MPM
Selectivity coefficients	
Nd ³⁺	4.3×10^{-4}
Pr ³⁺	8.8×10^{-4}
Er ³⁺	2.5×10^{-3}
Dy ³⁺	5.4×10^{-3}
Eu ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}
Yb ³⁺	2.7×10^{-3}
Sm ³⁺	7.3×10^{-4}
Cr ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}
Fe ³⁺	8.7×10^{-4}
Ni ²⁺	4.2×10^{-3}
Cd ²⁺	2.8×10^{-3}
Zn ²⁺	3.3×10^{-3}
Ca ²⁺	6.5×10^{-4}
Na ⁺	6.7×10^{-4}
Response time (s)	< 10
Linearity range (M)	1.0×10^{-7} – 1.0×10^{-2}
Limit of detection (M)	7.6×10^{-8}

Table 3. Comparison of the selectivity coefficients, linearity range, detection limit and response time of the developed Lu³⁺ electrode and the previously reported Lu³⁺ PVC-membrane sensors

	Ref. 11	Ref. 12	This work
	MPM	MPM	MPM
Selectivity coefficients			
Pr ³⁺	1.0×10^{-3}	7.8×10^{-4}	8.8×10^{-4}
Nd ³⁺	2.0×10^{-2}	6.5×10^{-3}	4.3×10^{-3}
Dy ³⁺	8.0×10^{-3}	6.2×10^{-3}	5.4×10^{-3}
Eu ³⁺	–	2.1×10^{-3}	1.0×10^{-3}
Er ³⁺	7.9×10^{-4}	7.4×10^{-3}	2.5×10^{-3}
Sm ³⁺	2.5×10^{-4}	8.5×10^{-4}	7.3×10^{-4}
Yb ³⁺	5.3×10^{-3}	5.8×10^{-3}	2.7×10^{-3}
Gd ³⁺	6.3×10^{-3}	4.7×10^{-3}	3.6×10^{-3}
Cr ³⁺	–	8.6×10^{-4}	1.0×10^{-3}
Fe ³⁺	–	1.0×10^{-3}	8.7×10^{-4}
Cd ²⁺	–	–	2.8×10^{-3}
Mg ²⁺	2.5×10^{-3}	–	8.2×10^{-4}
Ca ²⁺	1.6×10^{-4}	–	6.5×10^{-4}
Na ⁺	3.2×10^{-4}	8.7×10^{-4}	6.7×10^{-4}
Response time (s)	<10	~5	<10
Limit of detection (M)	8.0×10^{-7}	7.2×10^{-7}	7.6×10^{-8}
Linearity range (M)	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-6} – 1.0×10^{-2}	1.0×10^{-7} – 1.0×10^{-2}

response time, detection limit, dynamic range and serious interference of the proposed sensor were compared with the only previously reported Lu³⁺ sensor (Table 3)^{11,12}. As it is immediately obvious, the proposed Lu^{III} sensor in terms of selectivity coefficients, detection limit and dynamic range is superior to all previously Lu^{III} ion-selective electrodes.

Analytical applications :

The membrane sensor was successfully used as an

indicator electrode in the potentiometric titration of 25 mL of Lu³⁺ 1.0×10^{-4} M with EDTA (1.0×10^{-2} M) solution and the titration curve is given in Fig. 5. As can be seen, the amount of lutetium can be determined with the proposed electrode.

The Lu^{III} sensor was also used for the determination of fluoride ion concentration in three mouth wash preparation samples (with the same fluoride contents). 1.0 g of each sample was taken and diluted with distilled water in

Fig. 5. Potential titration curve of 25.0 mL from a 1.0×10^{-4} M Lu³⁺ solution with 1.0×10^{-2} M of EDTA.

a 100 mL flask and titrated with a Lu^{3+} solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$). The results (after triplicate measurements) are given in Table 4. Clearly, there is a good agreement among the declared fluoride content and the determined values with the proposed sensor.

Table 4. Determination of fluoride ions in mouth wash solutions

Sample	Labeled (mg/L)	Found ISE ^a (mg/L)
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Aquafresh, Brentford, UK)	1350	(1381 ± 22) ^b
Sodium fluoride mouth wash solution (Eurodont, DuroDont GmbH)	1450	(1478 ± 18)

^aSuggested Lu^{3+} sensor.

^bResults are based on three measurements.

Conclusion

In this work, 2-((2-(pyridine-2-yl)hydrazono)methyl)-phenol (PHMP) as an ionophore was used in fabrication of a potentiometric Lu^{3+} -selective membrane sensor which can estimate Lu^{3+} ions in the concentration range from 1.0×10^{-7} to $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ with the slope of $19.7 \pm 0.5 \text{ mV}$ per decade of activity. The constructed Lu^{3+} sensor based on PHMP, showed lutetium selectivity with low interference from common alkali, alkaline earth, transition and heavy metal ions. The membrane sensor was applied to the determination of fluoride ions in mouth wash samples.

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